

D4.11

Description of the hybridGEOTABS demonstration and case-study buildings

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Summary

The main goal of work package 4 is the development of both real-life and virtual test beds to implement, validate and demonstrate the hybridGEOTABS concept, according to the plan provided in D4.3. The demonstration buildings and the case-study buildings that populate these test-beds are described in this report. Earlier, D4.1-2 provided an overview of a wider range of hybridGEOTABS buildings, as well as the selection criteria and selection of the demonstration and case-study buildings, made at the start of the project. The underlying deliverable D4.11 provides a more detailed technical description of the selected case-study and demonstration buildings, including a description of the building design, the HVAC-design (incl. hydraulic scheme) and the HVAC control. In general, there is a multitude of very detailed data that describes a building design (incl. detailed descriptions, plans and technical brochures, in various languages). In this deliverable, we provide building descriptions in a more accessible way for the reader, finding a balance between the level of detail and the readability, focussing on those elements of the design that are most vital for the reader to know for a good understanding of the validation and demonstration results that are presented in related deliverables, of which an overview is provided in Figure 0-1.

Figure 0-1 Overview of WP4 deliverables – reading guide (source: D4.3)

An overview of the case-study and demonstration buildings for which a description is provided in this deliverable:

The virtual test bed includes one case-study hybridGEOTABS building for each of the four building typologies studied:

- an elderly care home: Ter Potterie, Bruges (BE)
- an office building: Infrax/Fluvius (BE)
- a school in Libeznice (CZ)
- a multi-family residential building: Haus M (CH)

The real-life test bed consists of at least three demonstration buildings (partially the same buildings as those populating the virtual test-bed), in which the hybridGEOTABS concept with new Model Predictive Controls is demonstrated:

- an elderly care home: Ter Potterie, Bruges (BE)
- an office building: Infrax/Fluvius (BE)
- a school in Libeznice (CZ)
- *an office building: Solarwind (LU)*

Remark that during the project, the demonstration office building was shifted from Solarwind (originally selected in D4.1-2) to Infrax/Fluvius office for practical reasons. Finally, near the end of the project, MPC was developed and installed in Solarwind in LU, making this a 4th and 'extra' demonstration building. As this becomes an additional building, the documentation and validation of this demonstrator is more limited than for the other three buildings.

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Nomenclature

Acronyms

AB	As-built
ACH	Air change per hour
AHU	Air Handling Unit
API	Application Programming Interface
ASHP	Air Source Heat Pump
BMS	Building Management System
BTES	Borehole Thermal Energy Storage
CAV	Constant Air Volume
CCA	Concrete Core Activation
COP	Coefficient of Performance
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
DHW	Domestic Hot Water
EER	Energy Efficiency Ratio
FCU	Fan Coil Unit
GEOTABS	system combining TABS and geothermal energy using a heat pump
GSHP	Ground Source Heat Pump
HP	Heat Pump
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
LMTD	Logarithmic Mean Temperature Difference
MPC	Model Predictive Control
PV	Photovoltaic
RBC	Rule-based Control
RES	Renewable energy sources
RMOT	Running Mean Outdoor Temperature
SCADA	Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition
SCOP	Seasonal Coefficient of Performance
SEER	Seasonal Energy Efficiency Ratio
SPF	Seasonal Performance Factor
TABS	Thermally Active Building System
VAV	Variable Air Volume

Symbols

A	state matrix
B	input matrix
c	CO ₂ concentration [ppm]
d	system disturbance
F	correction factor
i	instance index
k	step index
\dot{m}	mass flow rate [kg/s]
N	number of horizon steps
Q	heat flow [W]
T	temperature [K] or [°C]
u	system input
U	heat transfer coefficient [(W/m ² K)]
V	disturbances matrix
x	system state
z	slack variable

Greek symbols:

α	Heat flow weighting coefficient
β	Slack variable weighting coefficient

Subscripts:

heat	heating
cool	cooling
ref	reference
max	maximum
amb	ambient
init	initial
BTK	concrete
T	temperature
v	ventilation
c	CO ₂ concentration

1. Introduction

The main goal of work package 4 is the development of both real-life and virtual test beds to implement, validate and demonstrate the hybridGEOTABS concept, according to the plan provided in D4.3. The virtual test bed includes one case-study hybridGEOTABS building for each of the four building typologies studied: an elderly care home, an office building, a school and a multi-family residential building. The real-life test bed includes at least three demonstration buildings (and a 4th additional demonstrator). This deliverable describes these demonstration cases along with the implemented Model Predictive Control (MPC) strategies (in the cases where they are applied).

These descriptions are extensively used in Deliverable 4.7 to construct the detailed emulators that lead to the virtual assessment in Deliverable 4.9. Indirectly, the need of a set of new component models (reported in Deliverable 4.6) for the IDEAS library appeared. The development of the tested white-box MPCs (as targeted in work package 3) also made use of the information contained in this Deliverable, more specifically in Deliverables 3.1, 3.2 and 3.6. The implementation of the new MPC strategies coming from work package 3 in the elderly care home, the office building and the school is a cumbersome task. The followed timeline is also reported in this deliverable. Furthermore, the deliverable 4.4 documents the measurement protocol followed in the buildings, and D4.12 and D5.2 report on the results of these measurements.

This deliverable is structured as follows: each individual chapter contains the information concerning one specific demonstration case. Each chapter first contains the information regarding the building envelope key parameters and the heating, ventilation, and air-conditioning (HVAC) detailed information: the constructions information, the hydraulic schemes, the technical information on the individual production equipment, pumps, heat exchangers... Then, the detailed information about the original RBC controller (MPC in the case of the school) and the newly-implemented MPC strategy is given (the latter only for demonstration buildings). The chapter concludes with the timeline followed for the MPC implementation. Chapter 2 reports the office demonstrator (Infrac/Fluvius), Chapter 3 the elderly care home (Ter Potterie), Chapter 4 the school (Libeznice) and Chapter 5 the multi-family residential building (Haus M). Chapter 6 provides a more concise overview of the additional demonstration office building (Solarwind). Finally, the conclusions of the deliverable are drawn in Chapter 7.

2. Infrac / Fluvius office building, Dilbeek, Belgium

Figure 2-1: Infrac/Fluvius building – Pictures

2.1. Building

Infrac/Fluvius¹ is an office building constructed according to the low-energy building concept, resulting in a very high energy performance. This building contains open-plan offices, cellular offices and meeting rooms. Heating and cooling are provided by a heat pump installation connected to a ground-source heat-exchange loop running through an array of deep boreholes.

Solar gains are reduced by solar protection in the form of mobile side fins or overhangs above the windows. Internal heat gains are limited by the use of daylight sensors to dim the lighting during periods of sufficient daylight with the knock-on effect of reducing heat produced by the lighting during periods of peak cooling demand. The building is both heated and cooled by a system of thermally-activated concrete in the floor slabs. The fine-tuning of the temperature to the desired level is achieved through pre-cooling or pre-heating the ventilation supply air.

The building was designed to be a high performing office building. The demands are mostly met by TABS, using heating provided by the ground-source heat-pump and passive cooling provided directly from the borehole field. Further efforts to reduce the energy demands have been made by installing high-performance side fins, combined with a daylight control.

Architectural floor plans

Figure 2-2: Floor -1; Basement/parking. SOURCE: [1]

¹ Infrac was the name of the company that owns the building. During the project its name changed to 'Fluvius'.

Figure 2-3: Floor 0; Entrance, hall, conference rooms, server room and canteen. SOURCE: [1]

Figure 2-4: Floor 1; Open offices, individual offices and meeting rooms. SOURCE: [1]

Figure 2-5: Floor 2; open offices and meeting rooms. SOURCE: [1]

Figure 2-6: Floor 3; open office, individual offices and meeting room. SOURCE: [1]

Sustainability labels

The INFRA X building has E-level 45 (overall energy performance level) and K-level 21 (global insulation level) in line with the Flemish EPBD-implementation.

Building physical information

The main façade of the building is oriented south-west. The U-values for the outer walls and roof are between 0.18-0.25 and 0.14-0.15 W/(m².K) respectively. The windows have double glazing with a U-value of 1.0 W/(m².K) and g-values between 0.45-0.49. The window-to-wall ratio of the building is 19%. The building is equipped with an automated shadow system with the exception of the north-east façade. The building can control solar gains by means of movable horizontal fin shading on the 3rd and 2nd floors. Fixed horizontal fin shading combined with overhangs is installed on the 1st and ground floors. The air-tightness of the building is measured with an n₅₀ value of 1.3 ACH. The average annual net space heating and cooling demands are 28.23 kWh/(m².year) and 36.94 kWh/(m².year) respectively. The composition of the walls are:

- Outer walls: 2.2cm Fiberboard + 18cm Glasswool + 20cm Sandstone + 1.5cm Gypsum
- Roof: 6cm Grind + 16cm PIR + 27-33cm Concrete (depending on side) + 1cm Gypsum
- Roof 1st floor: 2cm Perliet + 14cm PIR + 37cm Concrete + 1cm Gypsum
- Floor ground floor: 2cm Woodwool + 8cm PIR + 32cm Holed Concrete + 5cm Screed + 55cm Air + 3.8cm Silicate + 1.2cm Tile
- Floor other floors: 37cm Concrete + 45cm Air + 3cm Board
- Slab on basement: 35cm Concrete + 10cm Screed

2.2. HVAC and RES

The hydronic schematic of the Infrac building can be found in Figure 2-7. The schematic is divided in several subsystems: supply (green), TABS (blue), ventilation (red), server cooling (cyan) and dissipation (orange).

Figure 2-7: Infrac hydronic schematic

2.2.1. Supply system

The supply heating system is composed of 2 ground source heat pumps. The source-side of the heat pumps is connected to an array of vertical ground heat exchangers. The sink-side of the heat pumps is connected to a water storage tank and to the manifold, from where heat is distributed to multiple emission loops. Supply of cooling is provided by means of two heat exchangers connected to the vertical ground heat exchanger array and to a dry cooling tower that can dissipate energy into the environment. From the heating manifold, the building can supply heat to the TABS (located in the ceiling, 6 cm from the surface) and the heating coils located within

the AHU and the ventilation ducts. The manifold is also connected to the cooling tower in case heat needs to be dissipated.

The ground source heat pumps correspond to the brand DYNACIAT model 200LG/LGP of 70 kW_{th} each and a nominal COP of 5.4. The heat pump works with refrigerant R410A. Each heat pump has a two-stage compressor that allows to modulate the system capacity. On the sink side, the system media is water, while on the source side a 30% propylene glycol-water mixture is used.

The ground heat exchanger is composed of an array of 38x94m vertical boreholes with double-U configuration. The boreholes are placed around the building with a relative distance between them of 6 m. The ground composition is mainly sandstone with an average conductivity of 1.4 W/(m.K).

The volume of the storage tank is 2.5 m³

The cooling tower is a Balticare model VFL 242-HX whose capacity is 150 kW_{th} and a variable-speed fan.

The two cooling heat exchangers can remove heat from the TABS and the AHU air respectively. The heat exchangers belong to the brand Alfa-Laval with LMTDs between 0.5-1.5 K. The nominal powers of the different heat exchangers are:

- TABS passive cooling exchanger (E004): 90 kW_{th}.
- Air cooling exchanger (E003): 106 kW_{th}.

The circulation pumps installed in the supply system correspond to the WILO brand. The types are as follow:

- P1/P2 Borefield pumps: IP-E 50/150-4/2 | 38 m³/h nominal flow | speed controlled
- P3 Heat pump condenser pump: Stratos 65/1-12 CAN PN 6/10 | 24 m³/h nominal flow | pressure difference controlled
- P4 Air+server cooling pump: Stratos 80/1-12 CAN PN 6 | 28.3 m³/h nominal flow | on/off controlled
- P5 TABS cooling pump: Stratos 65/1-12 CAN PN 6/10 | 21 m³/h nominal flow | speed controlled
- P11 Cooling tower cooling pump: Stratos 80/1-12 CAN PN 6 | 30 m³/h nominal flow | on/off controlled

2.2.2. TABS system (slow-reacting)

The emission system of the building is hybrid, with TABS as the slow-reacting system which provides the main load. The two-way valves before the 3-way valve determine the system mode. In heating mode, the TABS system takes water from the manifold and mixes it using the 3-way valve. In cooling mode, the TABS system extract heating from the building and dissipates it using the TABS passive cooling exchanger (E004). The two-way valves control the mass flow rate at each floor, and therefore the amount of heating/cooling per floor. If no heating nor cooling is needed, the system still circulates water at a minimum mass flow rate.

The installed pump in the TABS system (P7) is a Wilo IP-E 40/130-2,2/2 with 19.4 m³/h nominal flow and on/off controlled. Concrete core activation (CCA) pipes of TABS are made of PEX 20x2.3 mm and they are placed 6 cm from the ceiling surface.

2.2.3. Ventilation system (fast-reacting)

To provide a fast-reacting peak load, the system relies on conditioning the air from the air handling unit (AHU) using dedicated heating and cooling coils. The AHU takes and conditions the air from outside and distributes it to the different building zones through the ventilation ducts. Within the ducts there exist VAV boxes and small re-heating coils for the fine-tuning of the building. Nevertheless, not all zone ducts are equipped with the VAV boxes.

The AHU is a centralized double flux mechanical ventilation unit with heat recovery and free cooling bypass. The AHU fans are controlled by providing a prescribed pressure difference between the inlet and the outlet of the unit. The nominal supply air flow is 10000 m³/h while the nominal extract air flow is 8850 m³/h. An air flow of 1150 m³/h is evacuated through the toilet extraction system. Since the heat recovery is placed in between the heating and cooling coil, the heating coil requires an additional heat exchanger to work with a water-propylene glycol mixture, not allowing water freezing. The used heat exchangers in the ventilation system belong to the brand Alfa-Laval with LMTDs between 0.5-1.5 K. The nominal powers of the different heat exchangers are:

- Water-to-Glycol heat exchanger (E005): 34 kW_{th}.
- AHU cooling coil: 59.3 kW_{th}.
- AHU heating coil: 34 kW_{th}.
- Ventilation ducts heating coils (sum): 45.4 kW_{th}.

The installed pumps correspond to the WILO brand and the types are as follow:

- P6 Ventilation duct heating coils pump: Stratos 40/1-12 CAN PN 6/10 | 9.8 m³/h nominal flow | on/off controlled
- P8 AHU secondary E005 coil pump: Stratos 30/1-12 CAN PN 10 | 7.3 m³/h nominal flow | on/off controlled
- P9 AHU primary E005 coil pump: IP-E 32/160-1,1/2 | 7.95 m³/h nominal flow | on/off controlled
- P13 AHU cooling coil pump: IP-E 40/120-1,5/2 | 17 m³/h nominal flow | pressure drop controlled

The air is distributed towards the different zones of the building, allowing a fine-tuning control of the temperature. The nominal air flows per zone are as follow:

Floor 0:

- Hall: CAV | Supply 600 m³/h / Extract 250 m³/h
- Server room: CAV | Supply 100 m³/h / Extract 100 m³/h
- First aid room: CAV | Supply 50 m³/h / Extract 50 m³/h
- Canteen: VAV | Supply Min/Max 200/3200 m³/h / Extract Min/Max 0/3000 m³/h
- Conference room 1: VAV | Supply Min/Max 0/1600 m³/h / Extract Min/Max 0/1600 m³/h
- Conference room 2: VAV | Supply Min/Max 0/900 m³/h / Extract Min/Max 0/900 m³/h
- Storage room: CAV | Extract 250 m³/h
- Western stair block: CAV | Supply 90 m³/h / Extract 90 m³/h
- Eastern stair block: CAV | Supply 70 m³/h / Extract 70 m³/h
- Toilet: CAV | Extract 300 m³/h

Floor 1:

- North zone: VAV | Supply Min/Max 0/550 m³/h / Extract Min/Max 0/550 m³/h
- South zone 1: VAV | Supply Min/Max 0/400 m³/h
- South zone 2: VAV | Supply Min/Max 650/800 m³/h / Extract Min/Max 300/800 m³/h

- Meeting room 1: VAV | Supply Min/Max 0/300 m³/h / Extract Min/Max 0/300 m³/h
- Meeting room 2: VAV | Supply Min/Max 0/300 m³/h / Extract Min/Max 0/300 m³/h
- Storage room: CAV | Extract 50 m³/h
- Toilet: CAV | Extract 350 m³/h

Floor 2:

- North zone: VAV | Supply Min/Max 0/350 m³/h / Extract Min/Max 0/350 m³/h
- South zone: VAV | Supply Min/Max 550/1400 m³/h / Extract Min/Max 300/1150 m³/h
- Meeting room 1: VAV | Supply Min/Max 0/300 m³/h / Extract Min/Max 0/300 m³/h
- Meeting room 2: VAV | Supply Min/Max 0/300 m³/h / Extract Min/Max 0/300 m³/h
- Toilet: CAV | Extract 250 m³/h

Floor 3:

- South zone: VAV | Supply Min/Max 650/1600 m³/h / Extract Min/Max 0/950 m³/h
- Copy machine room: VAV | Supply Min/Max 0/300 m³/h / Extract Min/Max 0/300 m³/h + 200 m³/h CAV
- Meeting room: CAV | Supply 150 m³/h / Extract 150 m³/h
- Individual small office room: VAV | Supply Min/Max 0/300 m³/h / Extract Min/Max 0/300 m³/h + 200 m³/h CAV
- Toilet: CAV | Extract 250 m³/h

2.2.4. Server cooling system

The Infrac building includes a dedicate room to cool server units, using two racks that can demand a maximum load of 20 kW_{th} each. Each rack has a Wilo pump installed (P12, P14) model IP-E 32/160-1,1/2 with 5.73 m³/h nominal flow each.

2.2.5. Dissipation system

When the supply system runs out of passive cooling capacity, the GSHPs activate to provide cooling through their evaporators towards the cooling heat exchangers. Therefore, the heat generated by the GSHPs needs to be dissipated. An extra heat exchanger (Eoo6) with a capacity of 150 kW_{th} is installed from the manifold towards the cooling tower. The water is circulated from the manifold using a Wilo pump (P10) Stratos 65/1-12 CAN PN 6/10 with 24 m³/h nominal mass flow rate and on/off controlled.

2.3. Rule Based Control (original)

The building control of the INFRAx office building establishes an independent work schedule between the TABS and the secondary system. Whereas the TABS system works according to the building climate mode, the secondary system is dominated by the individual demand of each zone. A base set-point for the building is calculated with a heating curve as a function of the average outdoor temperature of the last 4 samples taken each 2 hours, which can be modified by the user using an offset on a per-zone basis to determine the zone set-point.

The building can be in one of 3 Climate Modes: Heating mode, Neutral mode or Cooling mode. Climate mode switch evaluation occurs once per day at 18h00. A switch would be effective if one of the following conditions is met:

Table 2-1: INFRAx cooling modes

Active Mode	Conditions	New Mode
HEATING	$T_{outdoor-average} \geq 10$	NEUTRAL
COOLING	$T_{outdoor-average} \leq 14$	NEUTRAL
NEUTRAL	$T_{outdoor-average} < 10$	HEATING
NEUTRAL	$T_{outdoor-average} > 14$	COOLING

Climate Mode switching can directly occur between Heating \leftrightarrow Neutral and between Cooling \leftrightarrow Neutral, but not Heating \leftrightarrow Cooling (dead band principle). In order to switch between Heating \leftrightarrow Cooling, the building must spend at least one intermediary 24-hour period in Neutral mode. At any time, the climate mode can be manually overwritten. However, this manual intervention is automatically reset after 24h (reverted to automatic regulation).

The comfort bound is difficult to define as it is an indirect consequence of the heating and cooling curves but it is around [22, 24]°C. The maximum CO₂ concentration is set to 800 ppm.

The action of TABS is dependent on the Climate Mode, and it works on a per-floor basis. In the Neutral mode, the TABS loop is continuously working in closed-loop with the two-way valves opened at the minimum level of 20%. During heating mode, water can be supplied from the storage tank to the TABS loop. The water supply temperature $T_{TABS_water_supply}$ is calculated following a heating curve based on a 3-point average outdoor temperature from the previous day and achieved through mixing with a 3-way valve controlled by a PI-controller. For each floor, mass flow rate is controlled with a PI-controller acting on a two-way valve. The mass flow rate is deduced from the difference between the supply and the return water temperature from the TABS, which is calculated from the difference between the measured and desired floor average temperature. During cooling mode, water can be supplied from the passive cooling heat exchanger, connected to the evaporator-side of the heat pump. Similar to the heating mode, the water supply temperature $T_{TABS_water_supply}$ is calculated using a cooling curve based on a 3-point average outdoor temperature. This temperature is subjected to a compensation factor and a condensing protection afterwards. However, this temperature is achieved by controlling the speed of a hydraulic pump just before the inlet of the passive cooling heat exchanger on the evaporator-side with a PI controller. The mass flow rate control is analogue to the heating mode.

The secondary system for INFRAX is air-based and it is dependent on the individual demands of each zone. The ventilation system is working on weekdays from 7h00 to 18h00, with a refresh system from 6h00 to 7h00. When the difference between the measured and the desired temperature of an individual zone is too low or too high, the ventilation system will act to reduce it. Several zones are equipped with VAV boxes, which can also compute a ventilation air demand based on CO₂ measurements. In this case, the largest demand is used. The AHU is programmed with a heating curve to supply air at a temperature around 18 °C. It is connected to both the storage tank and a heat exchanger linked to the heat pump on the evaporator side, therefore it can heat or cool. Each zone-duct is equipped with a small heating coil that supplies the remaining amount of heat power needed.

When there exists a heat demand, the supply air is post-heated after the AHU with the heating coils and air will be supplied at a fixed rate, hence dampers are not varying their position. These heating coils are equipped with a 3-way valve with a PI-controller. Depending on the zone, this PI-controller is based on the difference between the desired and measured temperature of the zone or between the desired and measured temperature of the supply air. This supply air temperature is calculated with a nested-PI-controller based on the difference between the desired and measured temperature of the zone.

When there is a cooling demand, the air is supplied directly from the AHU. In this case, in analogue to the 3-way valves of the heating coils, the dampers are controlled with a PI. Depending on the zone, this PI is based on either the difference between the desired and measured temperature of the zone or the difference between the desired and measured temperature of the supply air. For clarification, see Figure 2-8.

Figure 2-8: Ventilation system working schematic

The heat pumps of INFRAX use a simple hysteresis control whenever a heat demand is active, keeping the storage deposit at 32°C with a (-2/+1)°C band. The system is programmed to work only with one heat pump at a time, nevertheless if it is not able to reach at least a storage temperature of 29°C in 10 minutes, the second heat pump will become active to supply extra power. Any cooling demand is met without the use of the heat pumps (passive cooling) until the energy injected in the ground exceeds the amount that leads to excessive temperature

rise. When the temperature exiting the boreholes is higher than 18°C, the heat pumps are turned on in reverse mode (active cooling).

The cooling tower is connected to the supply collector through a heat exchanger and the tower only works to dissipate heat in some scenarios. These scenarios include an excessive water storage temperature or an excessive glycol temperature to the boreholes (both in passive and active cooling). The cooling tower works under PI-control to keep its outlet temperature at 29°C.

Furthermore, under adequate circumstances, INFRAx is equipped with controls to provide night ventilation during hot summer days and automated shading for the west, east and south façade to avoid overheating of the building.

2.4. Model Predictive Control

This section discusses the practical MPC implementation for Fluvius and it is a copy from D3.6. Section 2.4.1 lists the MPC optimization variables and the control variables sent to the BMS of the building and Section 2.4.2 describes the objective, horizon and constraints of the MPC.

2.4.1. MPC control signals

The optimization variables of MPC and the actual control signals sent to the BMS are summarized Table 2-2.

General remark: The current white-box MPCs are formulated as a non-linear but continuous optimization problem. Therefore, the optimization of on/off components is approximated by using a continuous signal in MPC and by applying a post-processing afterwards. Further development of TACO will allow direct mixed integer programming to optimize on/off control actions.

Table 2-2: Fluvius: MPC control signals in model and actual control signals to the Building Management System

	Optimization variables in model	Actual control signals to BMS	Remarks
AHU	Three-way valve opening heating coil	Supply ventilation set point	-
	Three-way valve opening cooling coil		-
	Modulation heat recovery wheel		-
	Pressure head supply fan	Pressure head supply fan	-
	Pressure head return fan	Pressure head return fan	-
Vent	Three-way valve opening re-heating coils	Postprocessing: PI controlling valve opening to track supply air temperature from MPC	21 re-heating coils. Some re-heating coils do not measure the supply air temperature. The zone temperature is then used instead.
	Opening VAV supply and return	Opening VAV supply and return	2x14 VAVs + 1 VAV. The same signals is sent to the supply and return VAV.
HYDRO	Two-way valves opening for each TABS circuits	Two-way valves opening for each TABS circuits	1 for each floor, so 4 in total
	Three-way valve to mix supply and return TABS	Postprocessing: PI controlling valve opening to track supply water temperature from MPC	-
	Two-way valves to switch between cooling and heating for TABS	Postprocessing: on/off	MPC assumes modulating valves while they are actually on/off valves
	Heat pump modulation rate	Temperature set point for heat pump	MPC assumes a modulating heat pump while in reality two heat pumps with each two non-modulating compressors are installed.
	Modulation of each circulation pump of borefield	MPC signal not used. RBC controls it	
	Modulation of circulation pumps for secondary side of heat pump, primary side of heat exchanger for cooling TABS and ventilation	Postprocessing: pump turned on if thermal power of circuit connected to it is higher than 5% of nominal power	3 pumps
	Modulation of circulation pumps of AHU: for heat exchanger for pre-heating coil, heat exchanger for the coiling coil, heat exchanger for heating coil	MPC signal not used. RBC controls it	3 pumps
SUM	# optimization variables: 49	# BACnet points: 147	

The Modelica model contains a detailed model of the Air Handling Unit (AHU) including the fans, recovery unit, heating and cooling coils. As the BMS already contained a well working control (after some manual tuning improvements) to track a set point supply ventilation temperature, we decided to let MPC control the set point instead of controlling each component. No loss of optimality is expected by this simplification. However, the supply and return fan pressure heads are directly controlled by MPC. While in RBC mode the pressure heads are kept constant during the day around 120 (return) and 200 (supply) Pa, MPC will lower it down to 30 Pa.

The ventilation system of Fluvius is further equipped with 21 re-heating coils and $2 \times 14 + 1$ VAVs to adapt the supply air temperature and the air flow per zone. While MPC optimizes the opening of the three-way valve of the re-heating coils in its model, the actual control signals sent to the re-heating coils are the air supply set point temperature. In the case where the re-heating coils do not measure it, a zone set point is used instead. VAV opening signals are controlled directly by MPC.

MPC also controls the hydraulic part of the HVAC. The opening of the two-way valves of the four TABS circuits is directly controlled by MPC. For the three-way valve which mixes supply and return water of TABS, a temperature set point is used instead as control variable. The control of the two-way valves to switch between cooling and heating for TABS are optimized directly. The resulting heat flow rates are used to decide which of the two-way valves is opened in practice.

The control of the different compressors of the heat pumps and of the borefield pump is a delicate task as a lack (or a delay) of flow to the heat pump will trigger an error and shut down the heat pump (which can then only be manually restarted). In this project we decided to leave those control variables to the BMS and to only control the heat pump set point temperature.

Finally, Table 2-2 indicates which circulation pumps are currently controlled by MPC and how the post-processing is done from the continuous MPC variable to the on/off control of the actual pump.

The total number of optimization variables is 49 while 147 control signals are sent to the BMS. The difference comes from the post-processing and from the fact some set points can only be indirectly controlled (e.g. PI set point can only be controlled by overwriting its min and max value).

2.4.2. MPC objective, horizon, and constraints

The MPC objective considers the energy use of production and distribution devices:

- The electric energy use of the heat pump
- The electric energy use of the air handling units (fans)
- The electric energy use of the circulation pumps

The MPC has the following constraints:

1. min and max operative temperatures ($[22, 24]^{\circ}\text{C}$ for most zones) and max CO₂ concentration (800 ppm) for each zone that requires comfort
2. min and max supply temperatures for the TABS and floor heating circuits ($[20, 26]^{\circ}\text{C}$) and for the supply ventilation temperature ($[19, 29]^{\circ}\text{C}$)

The number of intervals of the horizon is 14. The following adaptive step size is used: $\Delta t = [0.25, 0.25, 0.5, 1, 1.75, 2.5, 4, 8, 12, 16, 28]h$. The total horizon length is thus 74.25h.

2.5. Timeline

The timeline below shows the periods where MPC was running (number of days per month indicated in the table). The COVID lockdown, followed by a smaller occupation rate is indicated as well. For some period in 2020 there was an update of the BMS in where there were issues with the data configuration.

The numbers in the table show the number of days a certain event occurred. The blue indication gives an overview of the total per month (the more blue, the more that specific event occurred during that month).

As for COVID-19 we have indicated in red/orange/yellow the periods where occupation was not constant or well known.

	2018											
	january	february	march	april	may	june	july	august	september	october	november	december
MPC/RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC
COVID												

	2019											
	january	february	march	april	may	june	july	august	september	october	november	december
MPC/RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	9	30	29	5	22
COVID												

	2020												2021
	january	february	march	april	may	june	july	august	september	october	november	december	january
MPC/RBC	9	RBC	RBC	8	4	28	29	19	7	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC
COVID			RBC DOWN			20 40%	60%		90%	80%	20%	20%	20%

3. Ter Potterie elderly home, Bruges, Belgium

Figure 3-1: Ter Potterie - pictures

3.1. Building

A relatively high ambient temperature and consumption of domestic hot water make this home a very energy demanding building. Due to the 24/7 constant occupation rates regardless time of day, this facility was an excellent candidate to introduce the use of geothermal energy.

A BTES (borehole thermal energy storage) field is installed in the grounds in order to equip the whole building with concrete core activation. Two heat pumps in the basement and two condensing gas boilers in the attic provide the circuits that operate at a low heating mode and cooling circuits, that operate at a high cooling mode. The boilers can be activated as emergency power supply for the concrete core activation, and hot water production in the case of heat pump failure. All areas are supplemented with radiators as quick adjusting temperature elements, if necessary. The installed concrete core activation is utilised for both the heating and cooling of the building. There are no active cooling elements placed, cooling occurs passively.

Through the use of vertical boreholes (90 st - 75 m), the building provides its own energy for heat generation, thus reducing the need for fossil fuels. Fossil fuels are only utilised for the production of high temperature hot water. The vertical holes ensure the soil acts as an energy storage medium. During the extraction of heat, which occurs during the winter months, the soil is brought to a lower temperature. This free energy is obtained from the cooled soil and in turn is used to chill water used to cool the building in the summer months. Due to this interaction, there is continuous regeneration of the soil during a full year term. This guarantees the power supply required for both cooling and heating of the building.

Architectural floor plans

Figure 3-2: Floor -1; Basement/parking. SOURCE: [1]

Figure 3-3: Floor 0; Entrance, cafeteria, elderly rooms. SOURCE: [1]

Figure 3-4: Floor 1; elderly rooms and common areas. SOURCE: [1]

Figure 3-5: Floor 2; elderly rooms and common areas. SOURCE: [1]

Sustainability labels

The TER POTTERIE building has a K-level of 29 (global insulation level) in the Flemish EPBD implementation, representing a global U-value of 0.52 W/m²K.

Building physical information

The U-values for the outer walls and floors rate between 0,25 and 0,27 W/m²K. The flat roofs have a U-value of 0,25 W/m²K, the sloped roofs have a U-value of 0,16 W/m²K. The windows have a U-value of 1.69 W/m²K and are provided with double glazing at a U-value of 1.1 W/(m².K). A weather station is installed to measure the outdoor environment with the goal to control the HVAC systems and shading. The composition of the walls are:

- Floor of the basement floor (parking): 30cm Reinforced Concrete + 8cm Mineral Wool + 7cm Concrete + 1.2cm Tile
- Floor of the ground floor: 25cm Reinforced Concrete + 7cm Sprayed PUR + 5cm Mineral Wool + 7cm Concrete + 1.2cm Tile
- Outer walls:
 - 50cm external brickwork + 3cm Ventilated cavity + 12cm Mineral Wool + 16cm Reinforced Concrete + 1cm plaster
 - Aluminum cover + 22mm Multiplex + 2,4cm air layer with wooden frame + 18mm Multiplex + 12cm Mineral wool with wooden frame + 15 cm parament + 1cm plaster
 - 3 cm Nature stone + 2 cm air layer + 12 cm mineral wool + 19 cm reinforced concrete + 1 cm plasterboards.
- Basement walls:
 - 16cm reinforced concrete + 10 cm mineral wool + 9cm brick.
- Sloped roofs: 195 mm thick panel with rock wool and pinewood for support.
- Flat roofs: 7 mm bitumen + 15 cm foam glass + 33 cm concrete.

3.2. HVAC and RES

The drawing below shows the hydraulic scheme for the building.

Figure 3-6: Ter Potterie – hydraulic scheme

3.2.1. Supply system

The heat production consists of two ground source heat pumps and two gas boilers. The heat pumps are connected to a water buffer and several manifolds, from where heat is distributed to multiple emission loops. In the design of this technical installation, the supply of cooling was provided from the geothermal system transferred to the building system by means of two heat exchangers. A back-up chiller will take care of the cooling load in case the geothermal system would be exhausted (at the end of the summer). This back up system however is not yet installed.

There is one cooling manifold with two connections for cooling coils in the AHUs and one connection to cool the ground floor. The last connection on this manifold is a changeover connection, to supply cooling to the heating manifold (CCA-circuits). The heating systems consist of one manifold and one substation to provide heating (and cooling) to the TABS (located in the ceiling, 10 to 15cm from the surface) and floor heating.

Two boilers were placed to produce sanitary hot water over three heat exchangers to feed two buffers of 1000 l. Next to the sanitary hot water, they also produce the heat for the heating coils in the air handling units and the radiators in the rooms. These boilers have a backup function for the heat pump system as well.

The boilers correspond to the brand RIELLO model TAU N PREMIX 350 N and have a capacity of 346,7 kW at a regime of 80/60. The set regime for these boilers is 70/50.

The ground source heat pumps each correspond to the brand CARRIER model 61WG 090 of 89,6 kW_{th} with a primary regime of 3/0°C and a secondary regime of 35/45°C and a nominal COP of 3,80. The heat pump works with refrigerant R410A. Each heat pump has a two-stage compressor that allows to modulate the system's capacity. On the secondary side, the system media is water, while on the primary side a 25% propylene glycol-water mixture is used.

The geothermal system is composed of an array of 90x75m vertical double U heat exchangers. The boreholes are placed around the building with a distance of 6m between the several exchangers. The ground composition is mainly of sand (<46m). The deeper we go into the soil (>46m), the more clay is found. The average conductivity is 1.87 W/(m.K) and the undisturbed soil temperature is 12,6°C.

The volume of the buffer over the heat pumps is 1.5 m³.

The two free cooling heat exchangers belong to the brand FIORINI with LMTDs between 3-3.92 K. The nominal powers of the different heat exchangers are:

- Passive cooling exchanger: 260 kW_{th}.
- Chiller: 140 kW_{th}. (not installed)

The circulation pumps installed in the supply system correspond to the GRUNDFOS brand. The types are as follows:

- P1 Borefield pumps: 2 x TPE100-200/2-S | 75 m³/h nominal flow | speed controlled
- P2 Cooling secondary side: TPE80-210/2-S | 50 m³/h nominal flow | pressure difference controlled
- P3 Heating secondary side: 2 x TPE80-210/2-S | 50 m³/h nominal flow | pressure difference controlled
- P4 Floorcooling: MAGNA 3 25-80 | 4,5 m³/h nominal flow | pressure difference controlled
- P5 TAPS: MAGNA 3 65-150 F | 13,3 m³/h nominal flow | pressure difference controlled
- P6 Floorheating and cooling: MAGNA 3 25-120 | 4,5 m³/h nominal flow | pressure difference controlled
- P7 TAPS: MAGNA 3 50-120 F | 17 m³/h nominal flow | pressure difference controlled
- P8 Floorheating and cooling: MAGNA 3 25-100 | 3,6 m³/h nominal flow | pressure difference controlled
- P9 Boilers: 2 x TPE 65-190/2-S | 26 m³/h nominal flow | pressure difference controlled
- P10 Radiators: MAGNA 3 25-120 | 4,5 m³/h nominal flow | pressure difference controlled
- P11 Substation Radiators: MAGNA 3 25-120 | 4,5 m³/h nominal flow | pressure difference controlled.

3.2.2. TABS system (slow-reacting)

The emission system of the building is hybrid, with TABS as the slow-reacting system which provides the main load. The need for cooling and heating is given by the weather station which will put the building in heating or cooling mode. The change-over taps are controlled by this mode.

The pump of the TABS connection on the collector circulates the water through the TABS. The two-way valves open when the building needs heating or cooling from the TABS. The water is injected at the bypass with the circulating water from the TABS. In the neutral zone, the system still circulates water at a minimum mass flow rate.

The water temperature that the TABS need from the heating and cooling system depends on a curve that was made in function of the outside temperature, measured by the weather station.

Heating:

Outside T: -10 °C Supply temperature: 35 °C

Outside T: 5 °C	Supply temperature: 30 °C
Outside T: 20 °C	Supply temperature: 24 °C
Minimum T: 20 °C	
Maximum T: 35 °C	
Cooling:	
Outside T: 15 °C	Supply temperature: 20 °C
Outside T: 22 °C	Supply temperature: 16 °C
Minimum T: 15 °C	
Maximum T: 25 °C	

3.2.3. Ventilation system (medium fast-reacting)

To provide a fast-reacting peak load, the system relies on conditioning the air from the air handling units (AHU) using dedicated heating and cooling coils. The AHUs take and condition the air from outside and distribute it to the different building zones through the ventilation ducts.

AHU 01:	Supply: 1005 m ³ /h	Extraction: 965 m ³ /h
AHU 02:	Supply: 3370 m ³ /h	Extraction: 3330 m ³ /h
AHU 03:	Supply: 5575 m ³ /h	Extraction: 5115 m ³ /h
AHU 04:	Supply: 875 m ³ /h	Extraction: 875 m ³ /h
AHU 05:	Supply: 4985 m ³ /h	Extraction: 4705 m ³ /h
AHU 06:	Supply: 3295 m ³ /h	Extraction: 2880 m ³ /h
AHU 07:	Supply: 4285 m ³ /h	Extraction: 4085 m ³ /h
AHU 08:	Supply: 1435 m ³ /h	Extraction: 1375 m ³ /h
AHU 09:	Supply: 1390 m ³ /h	Extraction: 1120 m ³ /h
AHU 10:	Supply: 1325 m ³ /h	Extraction: 1325 m ³ /h
AHU 11:	Supply: 1675 m ³ /h	Extraction: 1675 m ³ /h
AHU 12:	Supply: 4000 m ³ /h	
AHU 13:	Supply: 1500 m ³ /h	
AHU 14:	Supply: 2700 m ³ /h	Extraction: 2700 m ³ /h

The AHUs are all double flux mechanical ventilation units with heat recovery. Heat wheels are installed for most of the AHUs. Only AHU 01 and 04 have plate heat exchangers. AHU12 and 13 are AHUs to compensate the air from the kitchen hoods.

The temperatures of the ventilation air: these are set by a curve based on the outside temperature.

Outside T: -10 °C	Supply temperature: 23 °C
Outside T: 20 °C	Supply temperature: 20 °C
Minimum T: 18 °C	
Maximum T: 25 °C	

For AHU12 and 13 the maximum temperature is fixed and set to 18°C.

The installed pumps for the circulation over the heating batteries are:

- P13 Ventilation heating coil pump AHU01: MAGNA 3 25-40 | 0,60 m³/h nominal flow | on/off controlled
- P14 Ventilation heating coil pump AHU02: MAGNA 3 25-40 | 1,80 m³/h nominal flow | on/off controlled
- P15 Ventilation heating coil pump AHU03: MAGNA 3 25-60 | 2,80 m³/h nominal flow | on/off controlled
- P16 Ventilation heating coil pump AHU04: MAGNA 3 25-40 | 0,60 m³/h nominal flow | on/off controlled

- P17 Ventilation heating coil pump AHU05: MAGNA 3 25-40 | 2,60 m³/h nominal flow | on/off controlled
- P18 Ventilation heating coil pump AHU06: MAGNA 3 25-40 | 1,70 m³/h nominal flow | on/off controlled
- P19 Ventilation heating coil pump AHU11: MAGNA 3 25-80 | 0,85 m³/h nominal flow | on/off controlled
- P20 Ventilation heating coil pump AHU07: MAGNA 3 25-40 | 2,30 m³/h nominal flow | on/off controlled
- P21 Ventilation heating coil pump AHU08: MAGNA 3 25-40 | 0,80 m³/h nominal flow | on/off controlled
- P22 Ventilation heating coil pump AHU09: MAGNA 3 25-40 | 0,80 m³/h nominal flow | on/off controlled
- P23 Ventilation heating coil pump AHU10: MAGNA 3 25-40 | 0,65 m³/h nominal flow | on/off controlled
- P24 Ventilation heating coil pump AHU12: MAGNA 3 25-40 | 2,00 m³/h nominal flow | on/off controlled
- P25 Ventilation heating coil pump AHU13: MAGNA 3 25-40 | 1,40 m³/h nominal flow | on/off controlled
- P26 Ventilation heating coil pump AHU14: MAGNA 3 25-40 | 1,34 m³/h nominal flow | on/off controlled

The circulation pumps are turned on when the two-way valve to the battery is opened.

The air is distributed towards the different zones of the building, allowing a fine-tuning control of the temperature.

3.2.4. Radiator system (fast-reacting)

As we have a global temperature setting with the TABS and a global fine-tuning on AHU level of the temperature per zone with ventilation air, we still need a readjustment at the level of each separate room to set the temperature to the desired wish for each individual. This is crucial for heating since these rooms are foreseen for the elderly people.

The supply temperature for this loop is set by the outside temperature:

Outside T: -10 °C	Supply temperature: 70 °C
Outside T: 10 °C	Supply temperature: 50 °C
Outside T: 20 °C	Supply temperature: 40 °C
Minimum T: 30 °C	
Maximum T: 80 °C	

3.3. Rule Based Control (original)

The building control of the TER POTTERIE elderly home establishes an independent work schedule between the TABS and the secondary systems. Whereas the TABS system works according to the building climate mode, the secondary system is dominated by the demand of each zone and the tertiary system is controlled by individuals. A base set-point for the building is calculated with a heating curve as a function related to the average outdoor temperature measured from 8hoo to 18hoo.

The building can be set in one of 3 Climate Modes: Heating mode, Neutral - or Cooling mode. Climate mode switch evaluation occurs once per day at 18hoo after the average outdoor temperature is known. A switch would be effective if one of the following conditions is reached:

Table 3-1: TER POTTERIE cooling modes

Active Mode	Conditions	New Mode
HEATING	$T_{outdoor-average} \geq 19,5$	NEUTRAL
COOLING	$T_{outdoor-average} \leq 21,5$	NEUTRAL
NEUTRAL	$T_{outdoor-average} < 19,5$	HEATING
NEUTRAL	$T_{outdoor-average} > 21,5$	COOLING

Climate Mode switching can directly occur between Heating \leftrightarrow Neutral and between Cooling \leftrightarrow Neutral, but never between Heating \leftrightarrow Cooling (according to the dead band principle). In order to switch between Heating \leftrightarrow Cooling, the building must spend at least one intermediary 24-hour period in Neutral mode. However, at any time, the climate mode can be manually overwritten. This manual intervention will then automatically be reset after 24h (reverted to automatic regulation).

The comfort bound is difficult to define as it is an indirect consequence of the heating and cooling curves but it is around [23, 25]°C except for the office rooms ([22,25]°C). No CO₂ concentration is measured. The reaction of TABS is dependent on the Climate Mode, and it works on a per-floor basis. In the Neutral mode, the TABS loop is continuously working in closed-loop with the two-way valves opened at the minimum level of 20%. During heating mode, water can be supplied from the storage tank to the TABS loop. The water supply temperature $T_{TABS_water_supply}$ is calculated following a heating curve based on the outdoor temperature. During cooling mode, water can be supplied from the passive cooling heat exchanger, connected to the evaporator-side of the heat pump. Similar to the heating mode, the water supply temperature is calculated using a cooling curve based on the outdoor temperature. This temperature is subjected to a compensation factor and a condensing protection afterwards. However, this temperature is achieved by controlling the speed of a hydraulic pump just before the inlet of the passive cooling heat exchanger on the evaporator-side with a PI controller. The mass flow rate control is analog to the heating mode.

The secondary system is air-based and is dependent on the individual demands of each zone. Ventilation is constant in use and night ventilation is working between 20:00-06:00. When the difference between the measured and the desired temperature of an individual zone is too low or too high, the ventilation system will act to reduce it. The ventilation air temperature is based on a curve based on the outside temperature. Night

ventilation hits in when there is a difference on the measured and desired temperature of 1°C and the outside temperature is not higher than 18°C .

The third system is purely a heating system. The radiators are active in heating-mode and neutral-mode and the supply temperature is controlled based on a curve based on the outside temperature.

The heat pumps of TER POTTERIE use a simple hysteresis control whenever a heat demand is active, keeping the storage deposit at 31°C .

3.4. Model Predictive Control

This section discusses the practical MPC implementation for Ter Potterie and it is a copy of D3.6. Section 3.4.1 lists the MPC optimization variables and the control variables sent to the BMS of the building, and Section 3.4.2 describes the objective, horizon and constraints of the MPC.

3.4.1. MPC control signals

The optimization variables of MPC and the actual control signals to the BMS are summarized in Table 3-2.

Table 3-2: Ter Potterie: MPC control signals

	Optimization variables in Model	Control signals in building	Remark
Mode	Mode	Mode	Mode is not optimized but it is defined by a weighted average outdoor temperature. When this average temperature drops below 16°C, cooling mode is activated, otherwise heating mode is used. When in cooling mode, if the heat exchanger for passive cooling delivers less than 1% of its nominal power, passive mode is activated.
AHUs	Valve opening heating coil	Supply air temperature set point	For the 12 AHUs
	Valve opening cooling coil		
	Modulation heat recovery wheel		
HVAC	Injection valve opening for each floor heating/cooling and TABS circuit	Set point temperature for supply of each floor heating/cooling and TABS circuit	-
	Heat pump modulation rate	MPC signal not used. RBC controls it	RBC defines the set punt temperature for the heat pump based on the maximum set point of circuits. MPC assumes a modulating heat pump while in reality two heat pumps with each two non-modulating compressors are installed.
	Radiator valve opening	MPC signal not used. In reality radiators have thermostatic valve	-
SUM	# optimization variables: 49	# BACnet points: 71	

The hydraulic system of Ter Potterie requires that the TABS are either connected to the heat exchanger of the passive cooling or to the heat pump. The mode is computed based on a weighted average outdoor temperature and MPC optimizes its control actions taking the mode into account.

The Modelica model contains detailed models of the Air Handling Units (AHU) including the fans, recovery unit, heating and cooling coils. The fans provide a constant mass flow with a night set back and they may not be optimized but the rest can be optimized. As the BMS already contained a well working control (after some manual tuning improvements) to track a set point supply ventilation temperature, we decided to let MPC control the set point instead of controlling each component. No loss of optimality is expected by this simplification.

Similarly, MPC optimizes the injection valve openings for the floor heating and TABS circuits and we decided to let MPC control the set point of the supply temperature of each circuit instead of the valve directly.

MPC optimizes the heat pump modulation while in reality, the heat pump control is entirely left to the original BMS. The BMS set the heat pump supply temperature set point to the maximum of the floor heating and TABS circuit supply temperature set point which boils down to the actions prescribed by MPC. Controlling the heat pump and its auxiliary systems (borefield pump, circulation pump at the condensor side, and valves) is a delicate task as the heat pump can quickly get into an error mode if the mass flow is too low. As the original BMS has proven to be correctly tuned and as the circulation pump with constant pressure head did not provide additional saving potentials, we decided to leave it untouched for the first MPC version.

Finally, the gas boiler set point temperature is not optimized as a constant temperature is required for the domestic hot water. While the valve opening of the heating coils (which are fed by the gas boiler) are optimized, the radiators are not included in the MPC model. This is because each radiator has its own thermostatic valve which is manually controllable. By leaving out the radiators, we force MPC to use the TABS, floor heating, and AHUs to achieved comfort, such that the radiators need not be used. During the heating season, the supply temperature to the radiator circuit will be decreased to limit the power of the radiators to a minimum as they are not expected to be necessary to achieve comfort anymore.

The total number of optimization variables is 49 while 71 control signals are sent to the BMS. The difference comes from the post-processing and from the fact that some set points can only be indirectly controlled (e.g. PI set point can only be controlled by overwriting its min and max value).

3.4.2. MPC objective, horizon, and constraints

The MPC objective considers the energy use of production and distribution devices:

- The electric energy use of the heat pump
- The electric energy use of the air handling units (fans)
- The electric energy use of the circulation pumps
- The equivalent energy use of the gas boiler

The MPC has the following constraints:

- min and max operative temperatures for each zone requiring comfort ($[22, 25]^{\circ}\text{C}$ for office rooms and $[23, 25]^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the other rooms)
- min and max supply temperatures for the TABS and floor heating circuits ($[19, 35]^{\circ}\text{C}$) and for the supply ventilation temperature ($[18, 24]^{\circ}\text{C}$ for office rooms and $[21, 24]^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the other rooms, except the cafeteria where the ventilation temperature can go up to 30°C).

The following adaptive step size is used for the horizon: $\Delta t = [0.3, 0.3, 0.3, 1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 4, 4, 8, 12, 18, 24]h$. The total horizon length is thus 78h.

3.5. Timeline

The timeline below shows the periods where MPC was running (number of days per month indicated in the table). For some period in 2020 there was an update of the BMS in where there were issues with the data configuration.

The numbers in the table show the number of days a certain event occurred. The blue indication gives an overview of the total per month (the more blue, the more that specific event occurred during that month).

The red zones indicate periods in which the COVID-pandemic took place. During these periods the elderly home remained in use.

2018												
	january	february	march	april	may	june	july	august	september	october	november	december
	01	02	03	04	05	06	07	08	09	10	11	12
MPC/RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC
COVID												

2019												
	january	february	march	april	may	june	july	august	september	october	november	december
	01	02	03	04	05	06	07	08	09	10	11	12
MPC/RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC

2020												
	january	february	march	april	may	june	july	august	september	october	november	december
	01	02	03	04	05	06	07	08	09	10	11	12
MPC/RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	RBC	11	18	RBC	8	10	26
COVID												

2021	
	january
	01
MPC/RBC	18
COVID	

4. Libeznice school, Libeznice, Czech Republic

4.1. Building

Figure 4-1: Libeznice school – pictures (© Andrea Thiel Lhotáková)

An elementary school for 240 pupils in 8 classrooms, which also has after-school activities. The building is a single-storey annular shape with an eccentric round atrium, surrounded by a multifunctional foyer, integrating a corridor, children’s lockers and a common area. The annular shape is inspired by the solar system. The school’s cafeteria layout allows easy rearrangement, creating space for performances, or lectures with film screening.

The building is equipped with TABS heating and cooling system (one circuit in the ceiling of the building), independent low-temperature ventilation units for each classroom and hot water circuit. The source of energy is ground coupled heat pump with heating power of 55 kW and cooling power of 65 kW. There are 6 boreholes on the primary side of the heat pump. The heat pump is operated in the three regimes i) heating, ii) passive cooling, iii) active cooling (compressor active).

The GEOTABS system is controlled by a predictive controller (MPC) that takes into account weather forecast, model of thermodynamics of the heat pump and TABS. Moreover, spot market electricity prices are included in the MPC problem formulation which results in a higher consumption in situations when the price of electricity is low (surplus of the electricity in the grid) and lower consumption in other moments (demand side management). The algorithms benefit from the huge thermal capacity of the TABS system.

Architectural floor plan

Figure 4-2: Schematic plan of Libeznice school. Source <https://bigsee.eu/libeznice-projektill/>.

Figure 4-3: Schematic plan of the roof of the building including 9 rooftop units for AHUs.

Sustainability labels

The project is an award winner of the BigSEE Wood Design Award 2018 and was nominated for the Mies van der Rohe Award in 2017.

Building physical information

As the building is designed in the round shape, there is no main façade orientation of the building. The U-values for the outer walls, floor and roof are on average 0.27 W/(m².K). The TABS piping is included in the ceiling of the rooms. There are three windows and one exterior door in each class. The windows have double glazing with a U-value of 1.2 W/(m².K). The windows are equipped with blinds that can be dropped down manually. The average annual net space heating and cooling demands are 50.7 kWh/(m².year) and 10.3 kWh/(m².year) respectively.

Building construction type	Heavyweight
Average U-value for opaque elements (roof, walls, floors)	0.27 W/m ² ·K
U-value of glazing	1.2 W/m ² ·K
G-value of glazing	0.7
Glazing area (% of facade)	50 %
Air tightness level / n50 air change rates	2,5 1/h
Orientation of main facade	Circular roundel building
Type of shading (e.g. manual)	No shading
Net space heating demand (kWh/(m ² ·annum))	50.7 kWh/(m ² ·annum)
Net space cooling demand (kWh/(m ² ·annum))	10.3 kWh/(m ² ·annum)

4.2. HVAC and RES

The hydronic schematic of Libeznice school can be found in Figure 4-4. The red lines denote supply water pipes for heating, the blue lines denote supply water pipes for cooling and blue dashed lines represent return water pipes. The green lines denote pipes with brine (water and salt mixture). There are 2 energy sources – ground coupled heat pump and electric boiler (only for back-up situations). There are 3 storage tanks – domestic hot water, heating and cooling storage tank, each with the volume of 500 litres. There is also an electric cartridge in DHW tank as a back-up heater.

Figure 4-4: Libeznice hydronic schematic

The system be operated in several operational modes:

- Preparation of hot water for heat storage tank
- Preparation of hot water for DHW tank
- Preparation of cold water for cooling storage tank – passive (without compressor)
- Preparation of cold water for cooling storage tank – active (with compressor)

There are couple of 0/1 signals that are controlled by internal controller of the heat pump (i.e., heat pump has its own algorithm for controlling the regimes). These signals are stored in BMS system (Mervis SCADA).

ZW1: electrical cartridge in DHW tank is on/off (it is a back-up heater, only for situations when heat pump does not provide sufficient heat)

ZW2: electrical boiler is switched on/off (if the heat pump does not meet load required by AHU and TABS, i.e., required temperature in heat storage tank)

VBO: operation of pump for boreholes (on the primary side of HP) (pump 1.1)

ZUP: operation of pump on the secondary side of HP (pump 2.1)

The additional signal BUP defines where to put heat, whether to DHW tank (BUP=1) or heat storage tank (BUP=0). In fact, if BUP is switched from 0 to 1, the three-way valve V₄ is switched to position A and pump 4.1 starts working.

i.e., when the HP is working and provides some heat, then VBO and ZUP are active.

The signals SP₂ and SP₃ distinguish between active and passive cooling. If SP₂=1 AND SP₃=1 then active cooling is active and if SP₂=1 AND SP₃=0 then passive cooling is active.

The configuration of three-way valves and operation of pumps determine one of the following regimes:

Heating (heat storage tank)

VBO and ZUP is active (VBO=1, ZUP=1), thus pumps 1.1 and 2.1 are switched on and three-way valves V₁, V₂ and V₃ are in position B. Signal BUP is not active (BUP=0), which means that valve V₄ is in position B.

Heating (DHW)

VBO and ZUP is active (VBO=1, ZUP=1), thus pumps 1.1 and 2.1 are switched on and three-way valves V₁, V₂ and V₃ are in position B. Signal BUP is active (BUP=1), which means that pump 4.1 is working and valve V₄ is in position A.

Passive cooling (without compressor)

SP₂=1 and SP₃=0 then passive cooling is active. VBO is also active (pump 1.1 is on) and ZUP is not active (pump 2.1 is not working). Moreover, pump 2.3 is working and valves V₁ and V₂ are in position B and valve V₃ is in position A.

Active cooling (with compressor)

If the passive cooling is not sufficient for cold supply to TABS and AHU, the active cooling needs to be activated.

SP₂=1 and SP₃=1 then active cooling is active. VBO and ZUP are also active (pumps 1.1 and 2.1 are on).

Moreover, in this regime pump 2.3 is ON and valve V₃ is switched to position A. Heat from secondary side of heat pump is stored either to DHW tank or heat storage tank. If both tanks are full, V₁ is changed to position A (normally is in position B) and pumps 1.2 and 2.2 start working, therefore the heat is stored in boreholes (regeneration of boreholes).

Heating/cooling mode: this is switched based on average outdoor air temperature. At this moment the heating mode is turned on when the average temperature from last 3 days drops down 12 deg C. The cooling mode is activated when the average temperature reaches 15 deg C – so there is some hysteresis in order not to change the regimes so often.

The set-point temperatures for heating and cooling storage tanks are controlled via BMS according to the ambient temperature. The set-point temperature for DHW tank is 50 °C for working days from 5:15 AM to 7:45 PM with the night and weekend (holiday) set-back 30 °C.

4.2.1. Supply system

The source of energy is ground coupled heat pump with heating power of 55 kW and cooling power of 65kW.

The heat pump type is Alpha Innotec SWP 581. Alpha Innotec is a German manufacturer of heat pumps (<https://www.alpha-innotec.de/>). The heat pump communicates with the BMS system using BacNet protocol.

The heat pump is equipped by a separate electrometer, therefore the electric consumption of the heat pump can be measured. These data are stored in BMS system (Mervis SCADA). Unfortunately, there is no calorimeter for measuring heat power on primary and secondary side, respectively. Supply and return temperatures on primary and secondary side of the heat pump are measured and stored in BMS system.

The heat pump can be operated in several operational regimes. All regimes are described in details in Section 4.2 above.

There are 3 heat exchangers in the supply energy system:

- Heat exchanger for DHW (E1): 60 kW_{th}, Δp=22.5/4.4 kPa
- Heat exchanger for borefield regeneration (E2): 75 kW_{th}, Δp=17.3/18.7 kPa
- Heat exchanger for active/passive cooling (E3): 60 kW_{th}, Δp=32.5/30.8 kPa

There are 9 circulation pumps in the whole system:

- P1.1 main borefield circulation pump with the nominal flow of 13.6 m³/h
- P1.2 pump for borefield regeneration (propylene-glycol side) with the nominal flow of 10.8 m³/h
- P2.1 pump on the secondary side of heat pump, nominal flow 9.7 m³/h
- P2.2 pump for borefield regeneration on the water side, 10.8 m³/h nominal flow
- P2.3 cooling pump, 14 m³/h nominal flow
- P3.1 AHU heating pump, 4.05 m³/h nominal flow
- P3.2 TABS circulation pump, 3.6 m³/h nominal flow
- P3.3 AHU cooling pump, 4.51 m³/h nominal flow
- P4.1 pump for DHW tank, 2.1 m³/h nominal flow

4.2.2. TABS system (slow-reacting)

The emission system of the building is hybrid, with TABS as the slow-reacting system, which provides the main load. There is only one TABS circuit for all class rooms and multifunctional foyer. If the heat from storage tank is delivered to TABS, the three-way valve V5 is in position B.

The installed circulation pump in the TABS system (P3.2) is with 3.6 m³/h nominal flow. The flow through TABS system is not changing, therefore the pump is working with the maximum speed.

MPC controls the desired supply water temperature to TABS. The maximum value is 45 °C in heating mode and minimum 16°C in cooling mode.

There is no calorimeter measured directly the TABS power, however flow as well as the supply and return water temperature of TABS are measured and stored in BMS (Mervis SCADA), therefore the TABS power can be calculated. The maximum heating power is up to 40 kW and the maximum cooling power is approximately 30 kW.

4.2.3. Ventilation system (fast-reacting)

To provide a fast-reacting peak load, the system relies on conditioning the air from 9 independent AHUs (for each class room and multifunctional hall) using dedicated heating and cooling coils. The heating storage tank prepares heat for heating coils and the cooling storage tank prepares cold for cooling coils. When the heating mode is active, the three-way valve V5 is in position B and the pump 3.1 is switched on. When the cooling mode (both active and passive) is active, the pump 3.3 is switched on.

The schematics of each AHU is shown in Figure 4-5. The AHU is a centralized double flux mechanical ventilation unit with heat recovery and free cooling bypass. The nominal supply and extraction air flow of AHUs for class rooms (AHU 1-8) is 780 m³/h and 2380 m³/h of AHU 9 for multifunctional foyer, respectively. There are 2 fans in each AHU (supply and extraction fan) both with the nominal electrical power of 340 W. The maximum heating power for all AHUs is approximately 47 kW in total and the maximum cooling power for all AHUs is about 21 kW in total.

Figure 4-5: Schematics of AHU in Libeznice school

The BMS controls the supply water temperature set-point for all AHUs, thus all AHUs use supply water with the same temperature. Each AHU has its own controller with the independent RBC logic. There is a PI controller, which controls the mixing valve in heating and cooling coil to achieve the desired supply air temperature that is set by MPC. The controller aims to use the most energy from recuperation and free-cooling through bypass, respectively.

MPC sets the supply air temperature set-point for each AHU, as well the desired speed of supply and extraction fan.

The following variables are measured and stored in BMS for each AHU:

- supply air temperature, extraction air temperature, class room temperature
- relative humidity and CO₂ concentration of extraction air
- supply and extraction pressure
- speed and pressure difference of supply and extraction fan
- dampers in intake and exhaust part (open/closed)
- position of control valves in heating and cooling coils
- return water temperature of heating and cooling coils
- position of bypass valve

4.3. Model predictive control (original)

The original MPC is also described in Deliverable 3.6 and 4.10.

The building was originally equipped with an MPC. The original MPC was in operation since November 2015 to October 2018. The original MPC did not allow AHUs to be controlled by MPC, as they were not connected to the central BMS. Thus, the original MPC controlled only the heating and cooling power to be delivered to TABS, while AHUs were controlled independently via RBC logic. The objective of the original MPC was to minimize the thermal comfort violation and TABS power. Moreover, there were two different MPC formulations including different dynamic models for heating and cooling. The original model, with MPC used, was the linear second-order dynamic model having one state the temperature of TABS and the second state the average temperature in the whole building. The manipulated variable was the heating/cooling power to be delivered to TABS. The model took the ambient temperature, solar gains and occupancy as the disturbance variables into account.

The main disadvantage of the original MPC is that it does not distinguish dynamics of individual class rooms, does not control both TABS and AHUs and does not control IAQ in the building.

The original MPC was a SW Python code, which communicates with BMS system using SoftPLCProxy protocol. The library CVXOPT was used for optimization.

4.4. Model Predictive Control (new)

Implementation of new MPC required several hardware and software changes including integration of AHU control system and extension of MERVIS database with measurement points from AHUs.

The aim of the new MPC implementation is to control both TABS and AHUs in order to control the whole HVAC system more effective. The following objectives are taken into consideration for the new MPC implementation:

- Unified model for heating and cooling
- Model for MPC should include temperature and CO₂ levels in individual class rooms instead of average building temperature
- Outputs of MPC (manipulated variables) are the supply water temperature for the TABS circuit and temperatures of supply air for each AHU
- AHUs are controlled not only based on temperature requirements but also according to CO₂ levels in individual classrooms
- Communication of MPC with BMS system using Mervis REST API instead of old SoftPLCProxy protocol.

4.4.1. Control strategy/signals

The control signals of MPC are also described in D3.6.

MPC in Libeznice school controls the following variables:

- desired supply water temperature to TABS (°C)
- desired supply air temperature of each AHU (°C)
- desired speed of supply and extraction fan of each AHU (%)

Together, MPC controls 19 variables. The list of all variables including corresponding MERVIS variables is stated in Table 4-1.

The output of MPC are TABS power and AHUs power, therefore some post-processing logic must be performed after each MPC calculation to obtain the control signals, which are communicated through MERVIS Scada interface with BMS.

The MPC is re-computed every 20 minutes, calculates the post-processing logic and saves the set points to MERVIS Scada interface. The post-processing logic is described in D4.10.

Due to noise at higher speed, the fans of AHUs can be operated only in range 0-60% except of AHU 9, it can be operated with the maximum speed.

Table 4-1: Libeznice school: MPC control signals.

Control signal	Corresponding MERVIS variable
TABS supply water temperature	ZS_Libeznice/BKT aktivní stropní konstrukce/Žádaná teplota výstup BKT
AHU 1 fan speed setpoint	VZT1 - Třída Merkur/Žádané otáčky FCS
AHU 1 supply air temperature setpoint	VZT1 - Třída Merkur/Žádaná teplota přívod FCS
AHU 2 fan speed setpoint	VZT2 - Třída Venuše/Žádané otáčky FCS
AHU 2 supply air temperature setpoint	VZT2 - Třída Venuše/Žádaná teplota přívod FCS
AHU 3 fan speed setpoint	VZT3 - Třída Země/Žádané otáčky FCS
AHU 3 supply air temperature setpoint	VZT3 - Třída Země/Žádaná teplota přívod FCS
AHU 4 fan speed setpoint	VZT4 - Třída Mars/Žádané otáčky FCS
AHU 4 supply air temperature setpoint	VZT4 - Třída Mars/Žádaná teplota přívod FCS
AHU 5 fan speed setpoint	VZT5 - Třída Jupiter/Žádané otáčky FCS
AHU 5 supply air temperature setpoint	VZT5 - Třída Jupiter/Žádaná teplota přívod FCS
AHU 6 fan speed setpoint	VZT6 - Třída Saturn/Žádané otáčky FCS
AHU 6 supply air temperature setpoint	VZT6 - Třída Saturn/Žádaná teplota přívod FCS
AHU 7 fan speed setpoint	VZT7 - Třída Uran/Žádané otáčky FCS
AHU 7 supply air temperature setpoint	VZT7 - Třída Uran/Žádaná teplota přívod FCS
AHU 8 fan speed setpoint	VZT8 - Třída Neptun/Žádané otáčky FCS
AHU 8 supply air temperature setpoint	VZT8 - Třída Neptun/Žádaná teplota přívod FCS
AHU 9 fan speed setpoint	VZT 9 - Aula a sborovna/Žádané otáčky Sborovna FCS
AHU 9 supply air temperature setpoint	VZT 9 - Aula a sborovna/Žádaná teplota přívod FCS

4.4.2. objective function, horizon, constraints

The MPC requirements and formulation of optimization task (objective and constraints) is also described in D3.6 and D4.10.

The aim of MPC implementation at Libeznice school is to keep zone temperatures as well as CO₂ concentrations in desired ranges and minimize the delivered power to TABS and AHUs at the same time. The maximum allowed CO₂ concentration in all classes is 1000 ppm. In heating mode, the indoor temperature in all classes should be higher than 22°C for Monday-Friday 6AM-5PM and 21°C during nights and weekends. In cooling mode, the desired indoor air temperature should be 23°C all the time.

The MPC objective can be formulated as follows:

$$\min \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} |\beta_{BKT} Q_{BKT}(k)| + \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \alpha_{T,i} (T_i(k) - z_{T,i}(k)) + \alpha_{c,i} (c_i(k) - z_{C,i}) + |\beta_{v,i} Q_{v,i}(k)|$$

$i = \{1, 2, \dots, 9\}$ (classrooms and hall)

N is 72 samples, corresponding to sample time of the controller 20 minutes and prediction horizon 24 hours.

subject to:

$$x(k+1) = Ax(k) + Bu(k) + Vd(k) \quad (\text{linear dynamics})$$

$$x_0 = x_{init}$$

$$z_{T,i}(k) \geq T_{ref,i}(k) \text{ in heating mode, } z_{T,i}(k) \leq T_{ref,i}(k) \text{ in cooling mode}$$

$$z_{C,i} \leq C_{ref,i}$$

$$Q_{BKT,cool} \leq Q_{BKT} \leq Q_{BKT,heat}$$

$$Q_{v,cool} \leq Q_{v,i} \leq Q_{v,heat}$$

$$0 \leq \dot{m}_{v,i} \leq \max(\dot{m}_{v,max}, c_i - c_{AMB})$$

$$\beta_{BKT} = 0.001$$

$$\alpha_{T,i} = 100$$

$$\alpha_{c,i} = 0.001$$

$$\beta_{v,i} = 0.01$$

where:

T_i is the temperature in the i -th classroom, c_i is the CO₂ concentration in the i -th classroom, $z_{T,i}$ and $z_{C,i}$ are the corresponding slack variables, Q_{BKT} is the heating/cooling power delivered to TABS, $Q_{v,i}$ is the heating/cooling power delivered to individual AHUs, $T_{ref,i}$ is the minimum desired, respectively maximum allowed classroom temperature, $C_{ref,i}$ is the maximum allowed CO₂ concentration, $Q_{BKT,heat}$ is the maximum heating TABS power

40 kW, $Q_{BKT,cool}$ is the maximum cooling TABS power 30 kW, $Q_{v,heat}$ is the maximum heating power of each AHU 500W, $Q_{v,cool}$ is the maximum cooling power of each AHU 500W, $\dot{m}_{v,i}$ is the mass flow rate of air in the i-th AHU, $\dot{m}_{v,max}$ is the maximum possible mass flow rate in AHU 390 kg/s and c_{AMB} is the ambient CO₂ concentration 300 ppm.

4.5. Timeline

The building and BMS were operational at the moment the project started, using the original MPC. During the project, following changes were applied:

1st May 2018

- AHUs ready for external control (MPC can set desired supply air temperature and speed of supply and extraction fans)
- Extension of the MERVIS database with measurement points from AHUs

15th October 2018

- Communication with BMS through Mervis protocol
- MPC controls both the TABS and ventilation system
- Temperature and CO₂ models for each class
- Grey-box model (RC model)
- MPC implemented only for heating mode

15th May 2019

- MPC implementation also for cooling mode

21th May 2019

- Bugs and errors in ventilation control system fixed

25th June 2019

- AHU fans can be operated with higher speed

5. Haus M multi-family building, Zürich, Switzerland

Figure 5-1: Haus M - Pictures (Photography courtesy of Johannes Marburg and Ursula Meisser)

5.1. Building

Haus M is a multi-family building located in Zürich, Switzerland. It is composed of five floors of dwellings, a kindergarten (named KiTa) located on the ground floor and a basement. From the second to the fifth floor there are six dwellings per level located around a large central atrium which contains the common areas (such as corridors, laundry rooms or staircases) for tenants. The first floor has the same distribution, but one dwelling (a studio) is replaced by the upper part of the main entrance of the building. There are 29 living units in total. Around 20% of the total area of each floor belongs to the common zones. The central area from the first floor till top floor, is an atrium: the areas are floorless in their centre, so all these zones are connected and combined through their empty spaces into one single central volume. On the ceiling of the central volume there are windows that can be electrically opened to renew the air. However, this action has to be made by hand. There is not any specific control to automate the opening-closing. The central volume and the basement are the only spaces without any control of temperature. The basement is included in the ventilation system while the central zone has to be ventilated by its windows on the roof. The conditioned net areas represent 6350 m² divided in 950 m² in KiTa and 5400 m² distributed in all residences.

Architectural floor plans

All levels of dwellings have similar geometry and distribution, thus there are six types of apartments and they are repeated along the five floors. The apartments, the KiTa, the central zone and the basement are colored on the floor plans. Note that the levels 2, 3, 4 and 5 are identical and represented by a single floor plan.

Figure 5-2: Haus M – Floor plans

Sustainability labels

“Mehr Als Wohnen” Baugenossenschaft (a housing cooperative) has engaged in several research projects all funded by SFOE (Swiss Federal Office of Energy) where most of the buildings are used as a “living lab” for various HVAC, building physics and energy studies in general. Haus M is one of them.

Building physical information

The main façade of the building is oriented to the south. The ratio between the area of the envelope divided by the conditioned area gives a compacity of 0.86. The U-values of the exterior surfaces of the building are summarized in Table 6-1.

Table 6-1: Haus M – U-values of external surfaces

Type	U-value [W/(m ² ·K)]
Ground floor	0.214
Facades	[0.35-0.573]
Roof	0.135
Windows – glazing	[0.7 – 1.1]
Windows – frame	[1.3 – 1.7]

The windows are triple glazed (g-Value ca. 0.5). The window ratio represents 40 % of the façade area.

5.2. HVAC, DHW and RES

The Figure 5-3 shows a simplified scheme of the energy systems related to heat in Haus M. In this building, there are two main functions. On one hand, the space heating, achieved by the GSHP and the floor heating and, occasionally, supported with the ASHP to reach high heating demands. On the other hand, the ASHP and the solar collectors installed on the rooftop have the function to produce DHW for the 29 dwellings and the KiTa.

The diagram also shows the type of fluids and the temperatures for each circuit.

The available information of the whole HVAC and DHW production systems is limited. The following sections in this document explain all the available parameters and all the known aspects regarding the HVAC and DHW systems, but the level of detail in the descriptions cannot be as precise as in the other buildings.

Figure 5-3: Haus M – Simplified scheme of the energy systems

5.2.1. Supply system

The building has two heat pumps. One of them is a 75-kW ground source heat pump (GSHP) which takes the energy from horizontal heat exchangers that cover an area of 885 m² located under the basement. The fluid in the borefield side flows at $4.89 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m³/s then the GSHP is on, while the water flows at $5.93 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m³/s on the TABS side ($1.45 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m³/s for the KiTa and $4.48 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m³/s for the apartments). This heat pump is exclusively used for floor heating both for the KiTa and for the dwellings. The flowrates of all loops were tuned once based on pressure drops. The technical information about the rest of the flows or pressure drops is not available. All loops are controlled by a heating curve that sets the return temperature of the water for the global flow. The GSHP has eight levels of modulation to adapt the power to follow the target temperature given by heating curve.

The other heat pump is a 64-kW air source heat pump (ASHP) that recovers part of the heat from exhausting air conducts of the ventilation system. The heat is used to keep the domestic hot water (DHW) at 53 °C. When there is DHW production, the flow in the water side is $2.56 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m³/s. It can also give support to floor heating when the GSHP cannot reach the target temperature. This situation is controlled by a valve between both major loops - floor heating and DHW-. It is a requirement to reach 53 °C in DHW consumption loop to let the ASHP give support to the heating system. There are 31 solar collectors on the rooftop of the building used to produce DHW through a heat exchanger. The total absorption area of the collectors is 77.81 m² and the thermal fluid flows inside them at $0.86 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m³/s. There was also a loop controlled by a valve that could connect the solar collectors to a heat exchanger for ground recovery when there is not any DHW production. This ground recovery loop is installed but it is not working since 2015. Consequently, solar collectors are only used for DHW production.

As the building only considers space heating and production of DHW, the system only extracts heat from the ground. Originally, there was a circuit to regenerate the ground by using the circuit of the solar collectors when they were not needed for DHW production. However, the system is not enabled, so there is not any way to regenerate the energy of ground rather than the natural regeneration process.

On the rooftop, there are also photovoltaic solar panels (PV) used for self-consumption. There is not any storage system for electricity. All energy which is not used is injected directly into the grid.

5.2.2. Floor heating as emission system

The space heating emission system in Haus M is floor heating in all conditioned spaces (dwellings and KiTa). The water pipes are 5 cm separated from floor finishing. This emission system is faster than TABS, hence there is not

any secondary system to complement the floor heating to ensure the correct heating demand of the building. The HVAC system is not designed to satisfy any cooling demand, but if in the future the owners decide to implement it, it would be possible to adapt the system to extract heat from the conditioned zones through the floor -floor cooling- and the GSHP to deliver the heat to the ground (active cooling).

5.2.3. Ventilation system

The ventilation system in Haus M is type C, which is based on mechanical extraction and the renovation of the air occurs through some grids distributed on the façade of the building. It consists in ventilators located on the top of the building that extract in total 6400 m³ of air per hour from all zones, constantly. That value represents around 1 m³/hour per m² of conditioned area. Fresh air enters the building through some ventilation openings located above the windows of all living units and the KiTa. Fresh air enters the building without any treatment, but all exhaust air conducts are connected to the ASHP for DHW production. Figure 5-4 shows a representation of the ventilation system in the building.

Figure 5-4: Haus M – Ventilation C with heat recovery through ASHP for DHW production

5.3. Rule Based Control

Haus M has a simple control for the heating based exclusively on a heating curve. That control is global, which means that the heating system of the whole building is controlled by only one parameter: the heating curve. The pumps are always working at the nominal regime during the heating period and there is not any valve that could control the flow of the hydronic loops, which were tuned manually. In this kind of control, the initial tuning of the hydronic loops is essential to have an acceptable thermal balance in all heated zones of the building.

The fine tuning of the pressure drops of the hydronic loops was done considering the measured temperatures in the different zones. Figure 5-5 shows some collectors of the floor heating in the KiTa where valves were installed to regulate the pressure drop of each loop manually.

Figure 5-5: Haus M – Details of the collectors for floor heating. The red valves were adjusted manually once.

The BMS monitors the temperature and relative humidity of each dwelling and the KiTa with hourly resolution. Every apartment has a temperature and humidity sensor located in the living room and the KiTa has one located in the centre of the biggest zone. The data obtained from those sensors is used to manually tune the heating curve, if necessary.

The heating curve calculates a return flow temperature based on the measured exterior temperature, affected by a correction factor. A privative algorithm calculates that factor. Currently, the equation that rules the heating curve, according to the parameters in the BMS, is the following one:

$$T_{return} [^{\circ}C] = \frac{-7}{30} \cdot T_{equivalent} + \frac{77}{3}$$

Where:

$$T_{equivalent} [^{\circ}C] = T_{exterior} + F_{correction}$$

$$F_{correction} \in (0, 15)$$

The parameters of the heating curve can be modified in the BMS at any moment. In the first years of the operation, the parameters were changed several times to find the best behaviour of the system. The correction factor also influences the heating curve, but it can only be modified by the developers of the algorithm that calculates it.

The GSHP has a modulation input controlled by the heating curve to set the return temperature. Every moment the controller is measuring the return temperature and if this is lower than the target temperature given by the heating curve, it increases the power of the heat pump to the next modulation level. If the temperature continues to be too low for some time, the following modulation level is set. For higher temperatures than the target one, the operation is the same and the modulation level is decreasing until the heat pump is off. If the maximum modulation level is reached, delivering the maximum power, but the temperature is still below the target for

some time, a control signal is given to a valve that can redirect part of the flow from DHW loop to floor heating loop. Additionally, it is a necessary condition to open the valve that the temperature of the final DHW equals 53 °C.

Each apartment has a device to allow the users to have a certain control on the flow of one of the floor heating loops that belong to the dwelling. The number of loops in a flat varies from 3 in the studios to 9 in the biggest apartments. The user's device controls the opening of an electronic valve that changes the flow in that loop. The rest of loops do not have any regulation system and the global flow in the whole building remains constant, so the real effect of the control is the variation of the flow in all loops, including the ones that do not belong to the controlled apartment. This situation conduces to an unpredictable behaviour when some users use it. In fact, the effect is not easily appreciable, so it is considered by the administrators of the building as a dummy control that may have a certain psychological effect on the occupants.

For the ventilation system, the control strategy consists in extracting air at a constant flow rate all the time. The air is extracted from each zone based on the design parameters of 1 m³ by m² of conditioned area every hour. As explained before, the system is C, so the air comes into the space through grids that are installed over the windows. Those grids have a mechanism to let the occupants close or open them manually, letting them to have control on the ventilation. Besides this, any occupant can open the windows to increase the ventilation in a certain room.

Regarding the domestic hot water, the ASHP extracts heat from the exhaust air until the DHW tank reaches 53 °C. When the target temperature is reached, the ASHP is turned off. When the temperature in the fluid in the solar collectors is higher than in the DHW tank, they transfer heat through a heat exchanger to the DHW tank. The tank is used to heat up the water from the grid, which will be used by the occupants in the building, through a heat exchanger.

5.4. Timing

The building is running under RBC logic since it was built in 2015. The first years the heating curve has been tuned several times to optimize the system according to the desired thermal comfort. The building is not a demonstration building in this project, thus no MPC is implemented (see D4.1-2-3).

6. Solarwind office building, Windhof, Luxembourg

Figure 6-1: Solarwind office - pictures

6.1. Building

Solarwind, is the spearhead of sustainable construction in Luxembourg. This building is based on a triple environmental certification, meeting the most stringent criteria in terms of sustainable development and eco-citizenship utilising the following sources of renewable energies: geothermal, biomass, solar, wind and water. The building is a 20.000 m² building with about 10.000 m² conditioned floor area. It is an office building housing different companies in about 76 zones designed for about 728 occupants.

It maximises the use of renewable energies (no fossil fuels are used) minimising the ecological footprint. The choice of the building envelope, solar orientation, materials and sealing were key. Renewable energy sources used: wind (urban wind turbines), solar (photovoltaic & thermal solar panels), biomass (wood pellet/shavings boiler for hot water production), geothermal energy & water (adiabatic cooling and concrete core activation). Heating and cooling of the building occurs via concrete core activation coupled with heat pumps in the winter and passive cooling in the summer. By combining geothermal energy with concrete core activation the energy consumption is optimised thus reducing maintenance costs. It is well ventilated (ID2) utilising a dual heat exchanger and adiabatic cooling utilising rainwater. The ventilation flows adapt automatically with air quality sensors that monitor the occupancy flow of the building.

The water cycle is sustainably managed: reducing consumption & harvesting rainwater (for adiabatic cooling, toilet flushing, etc.) and for the management of waste (zero bin concept, waste management flow). Reduction/regulation of operational costs via: triple glazing, artificial lighting equipped with motion detectors and brightness sensors; indoor blinds, outdoor shutters, green roof, and a green wall.

The building has its own website: www.solarwind.lu

Sustainability labels

The Solarwind office building has a triple environmental certification and is a passive building:

- BREEAM (very good)
- HQE (exceptional)
- DGNB (gold)

Building physical information

Building construction type	heavy structure / light facade
Average U-value for opaque elements (roof, walls, floors)	0.16 W/m ² ·K
U-value of glazing	0.69 W/m ² ·K
G-value of glazing	0.31 - 0.49
Glazing area (% of facade)	24%
Air tightness level / n50 air change rates	0.31/h
Orientation of main facade	South and North
Type of shading (e.g. manual)	PVs as horiz. panels S side, E&W automated louvre
Net space heating demand (kWh/(m ² ·annum))	19.5 kWh/(m ² ·annum)
Net space cooling demand (kWh/(m ² ·annum))	35.1 kWh/(m ² ·annum)

Figure 6-2: Solarwind – building physical properties table

The Solarwind building fabric is designed following the passive house standards and is thus a very well-insulated and airtight building. It has a moderate glazing area of about 24% with triple glazed windows and movable shading blinds (on the exterior in the east and west, and in the interior in north and south), combined with fixed

shading elements that carry the photovoltaics on the main (south) façade. A mechanical ventilation system with heat recovery and demand-control is applied. This results in a net heating demand of 19.5 kWh/m².year and a net cooling demand of about 35 kWh/m².year.

6.2. HVAC, DHW and RES

The drawing below shows the hydraulic scheme for the building.

Figure 6-3: Solarwind – hydraulic scheme

Aiming at a carbon-neutral and comfortable building, the building HVAC and energy systems use a multitude of renewable energy sources, as shown in Figure 6-4. The main heating and cooling system is a GEOTABS system consisting of four heat pumps for heating (120 kW) and a 240 kW heat exchanger for passive cooling, supplying heat to the heating coils of the VAVs and heat and cold to the TABS. The TABS mainly emits heating and cooling via the ceiling, as for the floors a raised floor construction is applied, which includes the ventilation ducts and supply. The upper floor is equipped with a chilled ceiling instead of TABS. Secondary heating emission happens via the heating coils of the VAVs and radiators, the latter being heated by solar thermal heat and biomass

combustion. The latter also provides heat for domestic hot water purposes. For cooling, the GEOTABS is assisted by cooling via the AHU, which receives cold from a heat pump and from adiabatic cooling using rainwater.

Finally, the buildings electricity is provided by on-site photovoltaic and on-site small wind turbines, and is coupled to the electricity grid.

Figure 6-4: Solarwind – Simplified scheme of energy systems

6.3. Rule Based Control (original)

The rule based control of Solarwind is complex due to the complexity of the hydraulic system. For more information, the reader is referred to the PhD-thesis of Filip Jorissen [2].

6.4. Model Predictive Control (new)

This section discusses the practical MPC implementation for Solarwind and it is a copy of D3.6. Section 6.4.1 lists the MPC optimization variables and the control variables sent to the BMS of the building, and Section 6.4.2 describes the objective, horizon and constraints of the MPC.

6.4.1. MPC control signals

The optimization variables of MPC and the actual control signals sent to the BMS are summarized Table 6-1.

Table 6-1: Solarwind: MPC control signals in model and actual control signals to the Building Management System

	Optimization variables in model	Actual control signals to BMS	Remarks
AHU	Supply bypass opening	Supply temperature	6 AHUs
	Return bypass opening		6 AHUs
	Three-way valve opening of heating coil		6 AHUs
	Pump pressure head of heating coil		6 AHUs
	Heat pump modulation		6 AHUs
	Indirect evaporative cooling humidity increase		4 AHUs
	Humidifier modulation	Supply absolute humidity	4 AHUs
	Pressure head supply fan	Pressure head supply fan	6 AHUs
	Pressure head return fan	Pressure head return fan	6 AHUs
Vent	Two-way valve opening of re-heating coils	Supply air temperature set point	64 re-heating coils
	Opening VAV supply and return	Opening VAV supply and return	64 x 2 VAVs The same signals is used for the supply and return VAV.
HYDRO	Three-way valve opening of AHU heating coil circuit	Supply water temperature set point	-
	Pump pressure head of AHU heating coil circuit	Postprocessing: on/off	-
	Three-way valve opening of VAV heating coil circuit	Supply water temperature set point	-
	Pump pressure head of VAV heating coil circuit	Postprocessing: on/off	-
	Three-way valve opening of TABS supply circuit	Supply water temperature set point	North & south supply circuits
	Pump pressure head of TABS supply circuit	Postprocessing: on/off	North & south supply circuits
	Two-way valve opening of TABS circuits	Two-way valve opening of TABS circuits	18 north & 11 south circuits

	Three-way valve opening of radiant ceiling circuit	Supply water temperature set point	-
	Pump pressure head of radiant ceiling circuit	Postprocessing: on/off	-
	Two-way valve opening of radiant ceiling circuits	Two-way valve opening of radiant ceiling circuits	8 circuits
	Two-way valves opening for heating or cooling	Two-way valves opening for heating or cooling	North TABS, south TABS, radiant ceilings
Production	Set point temperature of heat pump	Set point temperature of heat pump	-
	Pump supply pressures and valve positions for solar collector and pellet boiler	Set point temperature of hot water storage tank	
SUM	# optimization variables: 217	# BACnet points: 265	

The air handling units contain fans, indirect evaporative cooling heat exchangers, a heat recovery heat pump, a heating coil and a humidifier to passively and actively condition the supply air. Control signals for each device are determined internally in the AHU, based on temperature and humidity setpoints for the supply air, and two pressure setpoints.

The conditioned air is distributed to 64 pairs of VAVs (supply and return), each containing a re-heating coil before the air is distributed into the zones. MPC optimizes and sets the VAV damper opening and communicates the heating coil supply air temperature set point to the existing PI controller.

MPC can heat or cool the zones using the TABS. Groups of zones are connected to TABS circuits, each being controlled by one two-way valve. Those circuits are connected to one of two distribution circuits in the building. Each circuit (north and south) has independent temperature using a three-way valve and pressure control using a pump.

The eight zones on the top floor have a radiant ceiling, each controlled by two-way valve. The supply water temperature to all zones is controlled using a three-way valve.

The three-way valves of the north and south TABS and radiant ceiling circuits are connected to a separate collector. The collector is connected either to the heat production circuit or to the geothermal cooling circuit. The supply temperature of the heat pump is optimized. Other production instances like the solar thermal collector, the pellet boiler, circulation pumps are optimized but are not controlled directly. Instead a temperature set point for the hot water storage tank is provided.

6.4.2. MPC objective, horizon, and constraints

The MPC objective considers the energy use of production and distribution devices:

- The electric energy use of the heat pump
- The electric energy use of the air handling units (fans, pumps, heat pump)
- The electric energy use of the circulation pumps
- The equivalent energy use of the pellet boiler (scaling factor 1/3)

The MPC has the following constraints:

- Constraint on the heat pump maximum supply temperature
- Constraint on the buffer tank water temperature
- Constraint on the AHU supply air temperatures
- Constraint on the supply air temperatures in the zones (after the reheating coils) ([16,26]°C)
- Constraint on the TABS supply water temperatures
- Constraint on zone temperatures (the setpoints are chosen by the users and may change over time)
- Constraint on zone CO₂ concentrations

The optimization horizon consists of 13 intervals. Following adaptive step size is used: 1/4, 1/4, 3/4, 2, 3, 6, 6, 6, 6, 6, 6h, which adds up to a total horizon of 2.26 days.

6.5. Timeline

The practical implementation of the MPC is ongoing at the time of writing. To implement and test a custom communication layer using XML, and to verify proper operation before controlling the whole building, a phased approach is chosen. Following phases are identified and agreed with the building owner:

1. MPC running in the background without writing its control actions to test the stability of the algorithm (from 15/12 to 18/01/2021)
2. Control the VAV opening and setpoint temperatures of 3 zones on the 3rd floor (from 18/01 to 26/01/2021).
3. Additionally, Control the AHU, VAV's and radiant ceilings on the 4th floor.
4. Controlling the whole building.

At the time of writing phase 2 is ongoing. Communication issues regarding the AHU set points are being resolved together with the building control responsible.

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